

DETERMINATION OF PHYSICAL, CHEMICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SUBSTANCE CLOTRIMAZOLE A

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Relevance: Mycoses of the skin are a common global problem, affecting 20-30% of the world's population and ranking second among all skin diseases. Infection occurs through contact with infected people or objects, as well as in public places such as swimming pools. The prevalence of mycoses does not depend on geography or climate, but on factors such as age, immune status, the presence of chronic diseases, and hygiene. The incidence of diseases increases with age, especially mycoses of the feet, which can be found in every second patient over 70 years of age. The aim of the study was to determine the physicochemical and technological properties of the substance [clotrimazole A](#). Clotrimazole C₂₂H₁₇ClN₂ white or white with a yellowish tint crystalline powder. Soluble in alcohol 96%, slightly soluble in ether, practically insoluble in water. Clotrimazole is a broad-spectrum antifungal agent for topical use. Its antifungal effect is due to the disruption of ergosterol synthesis, a component of fungal cell membranes. This alters membrane permeability and causes subsequent cell lysis. It is effective against dermatophytes, yeasts, and molds, as well as the causative agent of pityriasis versicolor, versicolor and the causative agent of erythrasma. It has antimicrobial activity against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. Sieve analysis is the determination of the particle size distribution or particle size distribution of powders and granules by sieving them through sieves. Sieve analysis is performed by sieving material samples through a set of standard sieves with successively smaller openings from top to bottom, separating the material into fractions. Determining the particle size distribution of powders and granules is used in pharmaceutical manufacturing at various stages of production. Mechanical sieving is most suitable when the majority of particles are larger than 75 µm. The light weight of smaller particles results in insufficient force to overcome the surface forces of cohesion and adhesion during sieving, causing particles to stick to each other and to the sieve, resulting in the retention of particles that should otherwise have passed through the sieve. For such substances, air-jet or ultrasonic sieving may be more suitable. Sieving may be used for some powders or granules with a median particle size of less than 75 µm if the method can be validated. Flowability is the ability of particles of solid powdered substances or materials to flow under the influence of their own gravity. For the purposes of this General Pharmacopoeia Monograph, powdered substances or materials include pharmaceutical substances, excipients, their mixtures, intermediates, and other solid bulk materials that can be used in the production of medicinal products. The widespread use of powders in the pharmaceutical industry to create a wide variety of dosage forms of drugs requires a comprehensive assessment of their technological properties, including an evaluation of their flowability characteristics. Efforts to establish the relationship between various powder flowability criteria and the technological process of medicinal product production have led to the development of a large number of test methods for determining the multifaceted technological characteristics of powders, such as flowability, density, compressibility, porosity, and wettability. Hygroscopicity is the property of some substances to absorb water vapor (moisture) from the air. Hygroscopicity is characteristic of wettable hydrophilic substances with a capillary-porous structure

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and substances that are highly soluble in water, especially compounds that form crystal hydrates with water.